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Twelfth NDAC Report from Lund ObservatoryWP6000-7000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren, Söderhjelm)

Extensive simulations have been made of the determination of 'global parameters', including in particular Cowling's coefficients for the space-time metric (LO/055, 057 = C , C). A serious error was discovered in the earlier simulations (LO/034 = C), and much less favourable determination of these parameters is now indicated. The new accuracy estimates were also presented by Söderhjelm at the IAU Symposium No. 114 in Leningrad.

Practically all the software for WP6000-7000 is now operational, including the preparation and sorting of input data (abscissae), accumulation and solution of the normal equations for the set zeropoints and global parameters, and the adjustment of astrometric parameters with resolution of slit errors. A first test using abscissae for 10,000 stars observed for one year (part of the simulated data described in LO/048 = C) has been described in LO/056 (C). In that run, slit errors were successfully eliminated for 99.8% of the stars, and we can expect 100% success after ≥ 1.5 years of observation. A run with 2.5 years' observation of 10,000 stars (not using the MESH algorithm but with good *a priori* positions) was since made. The resulting distribution of errors in the positions, parallaxes and proper motions agree very well with the 'theoretical' mean errors from the coefficients of improvement.

Work remaining on this task includes interfacing with the set solutions, minor modifications (mostly cosmetic, possibly also in the file handling), further tests including also erroneous data and outliers, and documentation. Apart from the documentation, we propose to postpone these activities until the programmes are to be installed at DSRI.

WP8000: Double stars (Lindegren)

Work on the simulation software is planned to start this June.

Miscellaneous

A study of alternative approaches for dynamical smoothing has been proposed and outlined in LO/054 (C). The principles and limitations of HIPPARCOS data reductions were described in a paper presented at the INCA colloquium in Aussois (to be published in ESA SP-234). A short study of the 'phase bunching' technique for IDT preprocessing has been made (LO/058 = C), using simulated photon counts from ESTEC.

Working papers

- C Lindegren 1985-04-19: DYNAMICAL SMOOTHING, Task description for a (NDAC/LO/054) study of alternative approaches
- C Söderhjelm 1985-05-02: The Cowling globals in Step 2/3, erratum (NDAC/LO/055)
- C Lindegren and Söderhjelm 1985-05-08: Sample results from a test run (NDAC/LO/056) of Step 2/3
- C Söderhjelm 1985-05-24: The Cowling globals in Step 2/3, erratum (ct'd) (NDAC/LO/057)
- C Lindegren 1985-06-08: Experiments with 'phase bunching' for the IDT (NDAC/LO/058) preprocessing